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Frame conditions and testing processes for the implementation of PV-products in BIPV projects

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On the front page: Re-cladding of a façade in Romansorn, Viriden+Partners (source: BFE-SUPSI)

1 Summary

As already introduced in the SP4 of the Active Interfaces PNR 70 project, the developed and proposed BIPV products before the market transfer have to be characterized and tested for their intended use, according to the current normative framework. The first step in doing so is the identification of the requirements applicable on BIPV products, both as element for electricity production (such as a photovoltaic module) and as building elements, originated by European Standards and National Building Codes (building integration). A current question, that we are going to investigate in this work, is whether conventional PV modules (normally used in ground and on-roof power plants) can be also used as cladding element for the building skin, e.g. for facades and they comply with all the normative in force.

In Project 4 of the Active Interface umbrella project, the regulatory framework for BIPV systems has been identified with emphasis on BIPV requirements according to European Standards and Swiss National Building Codes. Thus, another dedicated report was finalized to collect the European regulatory framework applicable to BIPV products as electro technical and construction product.

This report contains the results of the investigation done in the framework of Project 4 WP1-4. The research will focus on the identification of the frame conditions and main aspects to evaluate the possibility to implement “conventional/standard PV systems” in BIPV projects, with the goal to point out issues, main questions, opportunities and missing gaps. Since this topic is often recurring in the real market and among operators, this report will contribute in clarifying this issue both from a methodological and practical perspective showing the “normative approach” needed for implementing PV as part of the building envelope, by also providing examples of specific technical requirements and some case-studies. Moreover, a discussion on the processes required for re-testing PV modules in BIPV application will be included.

This report is aimed to provide a basis for architects, building engineers, installers and manufacturers to clarify which is the approach to ensure the compliance with normative in force when an active BIPV component (conventional or not, is not so important!) is used as part of the building skin.

2 Introduction

The never-ending discussion and debate in BIPV field between standardization and customization of PV elements for building use, namely between the use of “conventional/standard” PV or BIPV products as building elements, is still looking for clarifications at both national and international level. Indeed, a conventional PV module could be generally installed as a BAPV system when it is certified in accordance with the IEC standards. However, in most cases a conventional PV module probably needs to be partially modified/customized to be used as a building element, in order to satisfy the specific requirements of the building skin, since it can be difficult to imagine that a standard PV product could be compliant with all the building requirements in different scenarios.

In particular, manufacturers, architects, researchers and building contractors are trying to find the best way to optimally balance the need of customization of a PV component (to obtain a product suitable for architecture and building integration) and the need to optimize, on the other hand, the cost-effectiveness in terms of production, performance, qualification/certification, etc... like it is already been achieved for standard products. It is not a simple task to merge and coordinate these very different fields since very often architectural design requires specific and tailored solutions for each single project, also considering the fact that conventional building products are going more and more towards a mass-customization as a common option available for architects and customers. Moreover, on the other hand, also PV products are more and more developed with advanced electrical and energy requirements (to ensure efficiency, reliability, safety, etc.), hence making changes on a “pre-defined” PV product can be not easy without introducing extra-costs in terms of manufacturing (e.g. related to production flexibility) and product’s qualification (e.g. re-testing for any customized solution).

Therefore, the main question that authors will try to answer in this report is: **is it possible to use “conventional/standard” PV modules for BIPV skin?** Since the goal of this report is to understand the potentials of application of “conventional/standard” PV modules for BIPV projects with regard to its normative compliance, after some definitions in chapter 3 aimed to clarify what a “conventional/standard” is in our discussion, the chapter 4 will report some of the key-topics related to the performance levels and qualification issues regarding the application for building skin. In detail, the mechanical and fire properties for facades application will be discussed providing a practical example. In chapter 5 some real case-studies will be examined to understand how the main constraints are related to the real building context/scenario and how the need to comply with complex standards and qualification procedures affects the main phases of design and construction. Finally, in Chapter 6, some aspects regarding testing procedures to qualify a BIPV system will be discussed with the goal to create a practical guide-scheme reporting possible references for operators.

3 “Conventional” PV products vs BIPV products?

This chapter is aimed at investigating three main aspects: firstly, what is and what is not meant as a “conventional PV” module in this report and which are the related standards, secondly, what is a BIPV module or system and the related standards and, finally, to introduce the main topics and discussions related to the possibility to use or not “conventional” PV modules in BIPV projects.

3.1 Conventional PV modules and systems

According to the International Electrotechnical Commission Glossary a photovoltaic module is a “*complete and environmentally protected assembly of interconnected PV cells*” (IEC 60269-6, ed. 1.0-2010). A PV panel is defined as a “*PV module mechanically integrated, pre-assembled and electrically interconnected*” (IEC 60269-6, ed. 1.0 (2010-09)). A PV system “*is a system comprises all inverters (one or multiple) and associated BOS (Balance-Of-System components) and arrays with one point of common coupling, described in IEC 61836 as PV power plant*” (IEC 61727, ed. 2.0 (2004-12)). What is worth to note is that the keyword “building” doesn’t produce any relevant result concerning BIPV for “standardized IEC terminology” in the IEC glossary (late access: 2017.04.04).

Therefore, in this report, on the basis of such a definition, a “**conventional/standard” PV module can be defined as a PV module that has not been developed for any specific building skin system or application**, but that is mainly developed and conceived as an electrical device and it has not been manufactured and qualified to satisfy a specific building role or requirements.

In particular, conventional PV modules are subjected to the electrotechnical certifications in accordance with the IEC standards as shown in Table 1. What is relevant to note is that, the design qualification of conventional PV modules is envisioned without taking into account any specific building applications (only the new IEC 61215-2:2016 declares that “additional requirements may apply for certain installations and climates” for static loads but there is no specific reference to building applications). Similarly, with regard to the module safety qualification, the IEC 61730-1:2004 (and amendments) states that “**this standard attempts to define the basic requirements for various application classes of PV modules, but it cannot be considered to encompass all national or regional building codes**” and also the recent IEC 61730-1:2016 sets that “this international standard defines the basic requirements for various applications of PV modules, but it cannot be considered to encompass all national or regional codes. **“Specific requirements, e.g. for building, marine and vehicle applications, are not covered”**. In addition to this, it is important to remember that conventional PV modules can have the CE mark (for EU market) if they are compliant with the standard EN 61730 that differs from the IEC 61730 standard for fire test and some minor modifications (PVSITES, 2017).

As a result, a conventional PV module has a datasheet with electrotechnical characteristics and performances without any information about building applications, as shown in Figure 1.

Before 2016	After 2016
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEC 61215:2005 – Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval • IEC 61646:2008 – Thin-film terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEC 61215-1:2016 – Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval - Part 1: Test requirements • IEC 61215-1-1:2016 – Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval - Part 1-1: Special requirements for testing of crystalline silicon photovoltaic (PV) modules • IEC 61215-1-2:2016 – Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval - Part 1-2: Special requirements for testing of thin-film Cadmium Telluride (CdTe) based photovoltaic (PV) modules • IEC 61215-1-3:2016 – Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval - Part 1-3: Special requirements for testing of thin-film amorphous silicon based photovoltaic (PV) modules • IEC 61215-1-4:2016 – Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval - Part 1-4: Special requirements for testing of thin-film Cu(In,Ga)(S,Se)₂ based photovoltaic (PV) modules • IEC 61215-2:2016 – Terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval - Part 2: Test procedures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEC 61730-1:2004 +AMD1:2011 + AMD2:2013 CSV – Photovoltaic (PV) module safety qualification - Part 1: Requirements for construction • IEC 61730-2:2004 +AMD1:2011 CSV – Photovoltaic (PV) module safety qualification - Part 2: Requirements for testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEC 61730-1:2016 – Photovoltaic (PV) module safety qualification - Part 1: Requirements for construction • IEC 61730-2:2016 – Photovoltaic (PV) module safety qualification - Part 2: Requirements for testing

Table 1. The IEC legislative framework for terrestrial PV module design and safety qualification

Manufacturer	MITSUBISHI ELECTRIC	
Model name	PV-MLU255HC	PV-MLU250HC
Cell type	Monocrystalline Silicon, 78mm x 156 mm	
Number of cells	120 cells	
Maximum power rating (Pmax)	255Wp	250Wp
Warranted minimum Pmax	247.4Wp	242.5Wp
PV USA test condition rating (PTC)	230.5Wp	225.8Wp
Open circuit voltage (Voc)	37.8V	37.6V
Short circuit current (Isc)	8.89A	8.79A
Maximum power voltage (Vmp)	31.2V	31.0V
Maximum power current (Imp)	8.18A	8.08A
Module efficiency	15.4%	15.1%
Aperture efficiency	16.7%	16.4%
Tolerance of maximum power rating	+3/-3%	
Static load test passed	5,400 Pa	
Number of bus bars per cell	4 Bus bars	
Normal operating cell temperature (NOCT)	45.7°C	
Maximum system voltage	DC 600V	
Fuse rating	15A	
Dimensions	64.0 x 40.1 x 1.81 Inch (1625 x 1019 x 46 mm)	
Weight	44 lbs (20kg)	
Number of modules per pallet	20	
Number of modules per container (40 ft. container)	560	
Output terminal	(+)-800mm (-)-1250mm with MC connector (PV-KTB4/6 II-UR, PV-KST4/6 II-UR)	
Certifications	IEC 61215 2nd Edition, UL1703	
Fire rating	Class C	

Figure 1. An example of datasheet of a conventional PV module (source: Mitsubishi)

It is important to highlight that the IEC 6125:2004 for design qualification states that “**any modification in the design, materials, components or processing of the module may require a repetition of some or all of the qualification tests to maintain type approval**”, whereas the IEC 61215-1:2016 sets that “Changes in material selection, components and manufacturing process can impact the qualification of the modified product. Material in direct contact with each other shall be tested in all applicable combinations unless equality can be proven”. In detail, the latter introduces the technical specification IEC TS 62915 for the details of retesting.

As a conclusion, it emerges as the existing normative framework for PV “standard” components clearly states that it cannot be considered to encompass all national or regional building codes and specific requirements, e.g. for building..., are not covered. Thus the building application cannot be only referred to the normative framework for conventional PV.

3.2 BIPV modules and systems

Several definitions of BIPV have appeared in literature, at both national and international level in last years. The acronym **BIPV** refers to modules and systems in which the photovoltaic element takes, in addition to the function of producing electricity, the role of a building element or construction product. A **construction product** is defined as “any product or kit which is produced and placed on the market for incorporation in a permanent manner in construction works or parts thereof and the performance of which has an effect on the performance of the construction works with respect to the basic requirements for construction works” and, specifically, its **performance** can be defined as “the performance related to the relevant essential characteristics, expressed by level or class, or in a description” (art. 2 CPR 305/2011). The basic requirements for construction works are set out in Annex I and they are the following ones: 1. Mechanical resistance and stability; 2. Safety in case of fire; 3. Hygiene, health and the environment; 4. Safety and accessibility in use; 5. Protection against noise; 6. Energy economy and heat retention and 7. Sustainable use of natural resources.

In recent years, the integration of modules in architecture is strongly evolving. New BIPV products, with their sizes and characteristics, are able to fully replace some building components. By BIPV element we mean a building component used as part of the building envelope (covering element of the roof, facade cladding, glass surfaces, etc.), sun protection devices (shading), architectural elements or “accessories” (such as canopies, balcony parapets, etc..) and any other architectural element that is necessary for the proper functioning of the building. This definition excludes therefore building “independent” or “overlapped” installations such as PV modules simply placed or mounted on pre-existing roofs or other PV systems merely attached to parts of the building that do not assume other function than the solar power generation.

The **BIPV concept**, as typical in building and architecture, involves two complementary aspects. The first one is the multi-functionality of the solar component that is the functional/constructive integration, while the second one is related to the aesthetic integration that is the architectural quality of integration, but this is not object of this discussion. According to the goal of the present report, we agree that “a BIPV component must firstly fulfill an additional requirement of the building skin (or have an additional function) besides energy production. Namely the PV layer/component cannot be autonomously removed from the building without compromise any technological/constructive primary requirement of the layering underneath or the whole building (that is, for definition, incomplete without the PV component)”.

A **functional integration** refers to the role of PV modules in the building. For this reason, we can speak about multifunctionality or double function criteria. Photovoltaic modules are considered to be building integrated, if they consist a building component providing a function as defined for example in the European Construction Product Regulation CPR 305/2011. The building's functions in the context of BIPV may be one or more of the following aspects:

- weather protection: rain, snow, wind, hail, UV radiation;
- mechanical rigidity and structural integrity;
- thermal and solar protection such as shading/daylighting;

Thus the BIPV module is a prerequisite for the integrity of the building's functionality (www.bipv.ch).

With the aim to clarify this concept, in 2016 the CENELEC Technical Committee 82 published a not-mandatory **BIPV standard**, the EN 50583:2016 Photovoltaics in Buildings (part 1: BIPV modules and part 2: BIPV system).

Specifically, this standard sets that “photovoltaic modules are considered to be **building-integrated**, if the PV modules form a construction product providing a function as defined in the European Construction Product Regulation CPR 305/2011. Thus the BIPV module is a prerequisite for the integrity of the building’s functionality. If the integrated PV module is dismantled (in the case of structurally bonded modules, dismantling includes the adjacent construction product), the PV module would have to be replaced by an appropriate construction product”.

In particular, the standard defines five application categories (fig. 2) depending on their type of mounting:

- integrated into the building envelope: yes/no
- accessible: yes/no
- sloped: yes/no.

Depending on both the main mounting categories based on a technological-building approach (roof, façade and external devices) and the main composing material (e.g. glass, membrane, metal, plastic, etc.), the essential BIPV performances are defined, as well as the main reference building standards as shown in Figure 3. Specific description of the European legislative framework and standards is included in the first report “European Directives and Standards applicable to BIPV products” of the Project 4.

In summary what is important to note is that:

- the CE mark for BIPV, as a building product and according to the EN 50583, has to be released in accordance with building product harmonized standards that comply with the CPR
- the CE mark that is already applied to PV modules is in accordance with the EN 61730 but, in this case, the performances that are declared are not related to building application.
- since the EN 50583:2016 is not a mandatory standard and not a harmonized standard (even though the unique normative concerning BIPV at EU level nowadays) some doubts still arise in the practice about the compulsory procedure to adopt for BIPV qualification
- typically the standard in force for the building skin components can be applied to BIPV to ensure an adequate performance (e.g. this is already adopted in many BIPV glasses) but...
- ...there are still some missing gaps in the building normative, especially concerning some technical requirement for BIPV (fire, mechanical), that calls for further developments

Category A:	Sloped, roof-integrated, not accessible from within the building	
	The PV modules are mounted in the building envelope at an angle of 0° - 75° with a barrier underneath preventing large pieces of glass falling onto accessible areas below	
Category B:	Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	
	The PV modules are mounted in the building envelope at an angle of 0° - 75°	
Category C:	Non-sloped (vertically) mounted not accessible from within the building	
	The PV modules are mounted in the building envelope at an angle of 75° - 90° with a barrier behind preventing large pieces of glass or persons falling to an adjacent lower area	
Category D:	Non-sloped (vertically) mounted accessible from within the building	
	The PV modules are mounted in the building envelope at an angle of 75° - 90°	
Category E:	Externally integrated, accessible or not accessible from within the building	
	The PV modules are mounted onto the building and form an additional functional layer (as defined in 3.1) exterior to its envelope.	

Figure 2. BIPV mounting categories, in accordance with EN 50583:2016.

Table 1 — General requirements for all categories of BIPV modules containing glass panes

CPR Requirement	Standards, guidelines, test methods	Comment
1. Mechanical resistance and stability	A.2	Depending on application and national requirements
2. Safety in case of fire	EN 13501-1	Classification standard. Manufacturer to declare the fire rating. Further requirements depend on application and country.
3. Hygiene, health and the environment		
4. Safety and accessibility in use	EN 13022-1	Only applicable for BIPV modules or PV insulating glass units to be bonded adhesively which are sold separately from the framework and installed under the responsibility of the designer and assembler. National regulations may define restrictions or additional requirements. ³
	EN 12600	For laminated safety glass only and if national regulations require the classification of pendulum body impact resistance: required for CE marking of laminated safety glass
5. Protection against noise	EN 12758	
6. Energy economy and heat retention		
7. Sustainable use of natural resources	EN 15804 CEN/TR 15941 EN 15942 EN 15978	See also Final Report of IEA-PVPS Task 12

Figure 3. Example of general building requirements for glass-based PV modules, from IEC 50583-1.

3.3 Is conventional PV suitable for buildings?

So far, the majority of **BIPV applications and projects** have been developed using the following product's categories:

- *Conventional PV modules* used in building application (almost exclusively for roofs) thanks to an adaption of some module's features (e.g. special frames for roof integration and water tightness). The certifications scheme in these product cases usually include IEC standards and, sometimes, the compliance with some building requirements (e.g. watertightness, fire safety, etc.). Generally speaking, such products usually have a low extra-cost in comparison to conventional PV. They are generally PV modules adapted for roofs, which represent the major part of the market. The compliance with some building requirements (e.g. fire safety, wind resistance, etc...) is often not specifically claimed or demonstrated by certificates so that the application in building skin is under responsibility of designers/installers.
- *PV modules declared as BIPV systems* (mainly with glass-based BIPV modules) usually produced by building industries capable to adapt an existing building product to make it active with PV (e.g. curtain walls or cold façade systems). In this case, the certifications scheme, adapted from the conventional building products, usually go beyond the IEC standards, including the building performances assessment and qualification (e.g. norms on safety glazing which are typically respected by glass manufacturers producing glass-based PV modules). Such products usually have an extra-cost in comparison to the not-active building system from which they derive, and they cannot be compared directly to a conventional PV module.

However, the main question of this report – is it possible to use a “conventional” PV module for BIPV project? – can be considered as a “misleading” question since, in detail, if we considered a “conventional” PV component (e.g. a standard 60-cells module sold on the market for PV plants) the real topic to evaluate its suitability would be, first of all, to define its application field within the building envelope, then to define the technological requirements and the legislative framework in force and, finally, to check if the component under investigation is compliant with the performance request arising from the (building, European, national, etc.) standards in force.

Therefore, within this methodological framework we can affirm that, in order to check the **applicability of a standard PV component in the building skin**, the main steps are:

- To define in detail the **technical element of the building envelope** where PV will have to be applied (e.g. mullion/transom curtain wall, cold façade, opaque discontinuous roof, parapet, etc.), its construction and functional requirements, the building typology and the intended use;
- To define the **performance levels and the reference normative** that such an application requires as a building component (applicable standards, European and local regulations) **to be correctly designed, manufactured and installed** as part of the building skin. It's remarkable to observe as these step can be defined for one or more phases of the process (from design to installation, maintenance, etc.).
- To check if the standard PV module satisfies such a performance request (does it respond to the requirements set by normative?), defining its definitive applicability as a building element

In general the **phases of the process** within which it is possible to make this assessment are the design phase (e.g. building architectural design, envelope engineering, etc.), the product's manufacturing (R&D, production, CE-marking, etc.), the installation as well as the operating-life. Each of these phases would involve different stakeholders, reference normative/requirements, goals and responsibilities. Moreover,

the same evaluation could be specifically focused on a **single technical requirement**, e.g. for mechanical safety, fire safety or acoustics. Thus the goal would be to assess if a conventional module satisfies a technological requirement for a building application.

It's relevant to note that the building requirements cannot be generalized but they are usually **local-based** since they're defined by the local normative framework (national, regional, etc.) depending on several factors:

- Building location (e.g. mechanical safety for snow, wind, earthquake or special requirements for durability, exposure, etc.)
- Building typology/function (e.g. acoustical, thermal or daylighting requirements)
- Urban area (e.g. specific requirements for visual assessment in some protected areas, or local conditions of shading, irradiation, etc.)
- Building skin technical element (e.g. roofs and façade have completely different technological solutions)
- Local urban/building planning and regulations

Moreover, very often the context generates further requirements that have to be respected (e.g. cost-effectiveness, aesthetics, minimum energy performance, etc.) at product and system level driving the development. In this transition phase for BIPV different approaches have been adopted at this regard so that the application field ranges from the application of conventional panels to the development of special components for single projects. Accordingly, and taking into account the normative framework described before, there is not a well-defined practice or procedure for ensuring the compliance of BIPV components with the existing normative and in most of the cases this topic is still under the responsibility of the different actors involved in the process.

In the following chapter, we'll focus the discussion mainly on the topic of the qualification of a BIPV module/system, intended for its manufacturing phase and its product qualification.

Figure 4. Conventional solar panels on LA school, USA, Brooks+Scarpa Architects

Figure 5 Conventional solar panels on multistorey building in Romanshorn, Switzerland, Viriden+Partners Architects

Figure 6 Conventional PV modules used as cladding of the envelope of a multifamily house in Chiasso, Switzerland.

4 Assessing the performance levels of standard PV products to evaluate the building applicability

As already introduced, in order to understand if a conventional PV module can be used or not in BIPV projects, it is necessary to evaluate if the component/system comply with the normative framework in force in the specific project context and regarding the specific building skin system, the material and technical application. Indeed, since BIPV modules by definition should be tested and qualified in accordance with both electrotechnical and building standards for their intended use, conventional PV modules to be used as construction elements should satisfy, accordingly, the building requirements needed for the functionality of the building skin and the consequent normative set applicable.

In this chapter the topic of performance levels of conventional PV for BIPV is discussed in paragraph 4.1, starting by briefly introducing which are the basic requirements of a BIPV product (this topic is object of another report within Project 04). Then, paragraph 4.2 will better describe the qualification issues that can arise when a conventional PV product is evaluated for building use, by giving a more detailed example for some specific technical requirements.

4.1 Performance levels of BIPV according to construction normative

As introduced in paragraph 3.2, photovoltaic modules are considered to be building integrated, if they constitute a building component providing a function as defined for example in the European Construction Product Regulation CPR 305/2011. Specifically, the EN 50583:2016 provides a collection of both electrotechnical and building standards that are relevant for BIPV product depending on their mounting category and their main material.

To clarify this concept, in this sub-paragraph a BIPV glass module is taken as an example but the same approach can be extended to other BIPV products with other mounting categories and other main materials.

In this case, table 2 shows the reference building standards of a BIPV glass modules when it is used as a skylight accessible from inside, in addition to the IEC standards. This means that a glass-based BIPV module to be installed as glazing of a skylight accessible from inside shall:

- be tested in accordance with the IEC 61215 and IEC 61730,
- be able to stand the static load defined in accordance with the EN 14449 and the Eurocodes,
- be tested in order to obtain the fire rating classification,
- be tested in accordance to the EN 12600 for building safety,
- be tested for protection against noise and for the sustainable use of natural resources.

In particular, figure 7 shows two certificates for a **BIPV glass**. This BIPV technology is today the most advanced solution ready for the market. On one hand, the BIPV glass module is certificated as a PV module in accordance to the IEC 61215:500 and IEC 61730-2:2012. On the other hand, the BIPV glass module is considered as a building product and hence it is subjected to the pendulum body impact test (in accordance to the EN 12600) as required by the harmonized standard EN 14449 “Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass — Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard” to distinguish laminated glass from laminated safety glass. In this case the EN50583 is respected and the BIPV component is compliant with all the existing standards, a part from eventual local normative setting more strict rules.

In conclusion, it arises that the approach set in the BIPV standard EN 50583-1:2016 for glass modules so far requires a twofold certification: one for the PV electro-technical requirements and another one for the building product “laminated glass” for building uses.

However, this doesn’t cover a general applicability for the building skin of this BIPV component since a still open topic is the ***need to evaluate the suitability of the BIPV glass module for a specific project*** (e.g. for defining the ability to stand mechanical loads such as snow/winds defined in accordance to Eurocodes and/or local codes in the specific context. It’s evident for example that the safety for wind load depends on the actions in force that vary according to location!).

Requirement	Standards, guidelines, test methods	Comment
1.Mechanical resistance and stability	EN 1990 EN 1991 EN 1993 EN 1999 Local codes hEN 14449	General: As building construction products, BIPV modules have to be designed to comply with the wind, snow and mechanical loads as well as other requirements set out in the Eurocodes EN 1990, EN 1991, EN 1993 and EN 1999. Glass modules: glass-based BIPV modules shall comply with the respective product standards for glass in buildings. For laminated glass apply hEN 14449.
2.Safety in case of fire		General: Manufacturer to declare the fire rating in accordance with the standard EN 13501-1 for classification. Further requirements depend on application and country.
3.Hygiene, health and the environment		
4.Safety and accessibility in use	EN 12600	General: the classification of pendulum body impact resistance in accordance with EN 12600 is required for CE marking
5.Protection against noise	EN 12758	
6.Energy economy and heat retention		
7.Sustainable use of natural resources	EN 15804 CEN/TR 15941 EN 15942 EN 15978	

Table 2. Example of reference standards for glass-based BIPV modules for skylights accessible from inside

Figure 7. Certificates for a BIPV glass module. Left: certificate in accordance to the IEC 61215:500 and IEC 61730-2:2012. Right: test report for assessing the pendulum body impact resistance (in accordance to the EN 12600), necessary to distinguish laminated glass from laminated safety glass.

4.2 Performance-based assessment for the applicability of conventional PV in building skin

As already discussed, when PV modules are compliant with electro technical standards, they can be surely used for conventional PV plants (such as open fields or Building Added Photovoltaics, where PV is simply added and overlapped to the building envelope without any building role) but they are not generally suitable for Building Integrated Photovoltaic (BIPV) installations due to the fact that **IEC standards do not set building requirements**. Indeed, as stated in the EN 50583-1:2016, **if a PV module is used for building integrated PV installations, it has to perform as a building element**, at least for the role that it is going to assume.

As for BIPV products, also for conventional PV products to be used in buildings it is necessary to identify the **intended final application in the building envelope** and the **main module's material** in order to assess and verify the compliancy with the building requirements. In particular, such requirements arise from the legislative framework about buildings and building's products and only if the performances of the conventional PV modules fulfil these requirements, the conventional PV product/system can be applied in the BIPV skin.

In order to clarify this methodology, the following sub-paragraphs provides some examples and hints for mechanical and fire requirements, in order to define a procedure to evaluate if a conventional PV panel can be used in BIPV projects.

4.2.1 Mechanical requirements of glass PV modules for BIPV facade

When **glass PV modules are used in the building envelope**, the requirements on the construction safety and the mechanical behaviour are particularly significant in comparison to conventional PV plants since **in their final use they constitute building elements**.

In particular, the mechanical requirements can be identified for two different levels: the module/product level and the envelope system level. Indeed, when PV glass modules (which are generally laminated glass) are installed as glazing elements of facades, they shall be compliant with the harmonised technical

specifications EN 14449 “Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass — Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard”. Moreover, depending on the mounting structure and fixing configurations, the whole envelope system should ensure mechanical safety and adequate operational conditions (e.g. adequate resistance preventing excessive deflections) along with the safety of users indoor or outside the building. Specifically, for this example, conventional glass PV modules are supposed to be installed as a glazing elements of a double skin façade and, in the following sections, a first analysis of the mechanical requirements at the module/product level is described, as well as a second analysis related to the mechanical requirements at the envelope system level.

4.2.1.1 Module/product level

As for BIPV product (see paragraph 4.1), when conventional glass PV module are installed as glazing elements of a double skin façade, they shall have both the IEC certification for PV products and the certification in accordance with the EN 14449.

In particular, the IEC 61215 procedure sets that the mechanical ability of the PV module to withstand a minimum static load (e.g. wind or snow), that is in the amount of 2'400 Pa (equals to 250 kg/m²), without electrical damages, shall be verified. On the “building product” side, the EN 14449 requires the evaluation of the mechanical resistance against wind, snow, permanent and imposed load in accordance with the design standards for glass (e.g. prEN 13474 or prEN 16612) which set that the design load shall be defined in accordance with the Eurocodes.

4.2.1.2 Envelope system level

In addition to the mechanical requirements that have to be fulfilled at the module/product level, also the mechanical requirements of the double skin facade with PV modules shall be fulfilled. In detail, a double skin façade is considered as a curtain wall, in accordance with the definitions of the EN 13830:2003.

Specifically, this standard states that the curtain wall kit shall be able to withstand the wind load **without damages or permanent deformations**. In particular, the wind load shall be determined in accordance with the Eurocode “Actions on structures - General actions - Part 1-4: Wind actions” with the specific coefficients for the determination of the wind pressure load, that are developed at the national level. In Switzerland, for instance, it is possible to determine the wind load thanks to the standard SIA 261:2014 “Actions on Structures” but the load will depend on:

- Geographical location,
- Terrain category,
- Building height and form.

Therefore, the load (and the consequent suitability of the pre-defined component for the application considered) can vary from building to building and depending on the location. For this reason, it is fundamental to verify whether the wind load can be “tolerated” by the double skin façade under consideration both in terms of resistance, limit states, etc. i.e. to verify that also the **maximum deflections** of both structures (e.g. mounting structures) and glazing elements **are lower than the ones set in the reference standards**. It's evident that such a requirements are not defined and assessed for a conventional PV panel!

In conclusion, the use of glass PV products for BIPV (e.g. of a glass-glass module produced as a standard PV component) shall be subjected to a set of specific evaluations , just for the mechanical requirements, that are established for the envelope's system form the regulatory framework in force for the building sector.

It's not possible to define a priori whether the standard element is applicable since the IEC mechanical static load test is not meant to determine the suitability of conventional glass PV modules for building projects. Generally this requirement is evaluated by façade engineers during the design phase through a specific FEM analysis of the façade system that consequently set out the main features of the component/system (e.g. glass thickness, glass typology, encapsulant, etc..) or verify the suitability of a pre-defined component through a reverse engineering process.

For other details, see also “Saretta, E., Bonomo, P., Frontini, F. (2016). *Laminated BIPV glass: approaches for the integration in the building skin*. In Jens Schneider and Bernhard Weller (Eds.), *Engineered Transparency 2016: Glass in Architecture and Structural Engineering (363-372)*. Ernst&Sohn. Print ISBN: 978-3-433-03187-2”.

4.2.2 Fire safety requirements of PV modules for BIPV facades

The use of glass PV modules in the building's envelope involves the PV module to be considered also as a building element. Similar to the mechanical requirements, also fire safety requirements can be identified for two different levels: the module/product level and the envelope system level.

When fire safety has to be assessed, two main concepts shall be considered at least:

- Fire resistance
- Reaction to fire

This topic is described and discussed in greater detail in the report “Fire safety of BIPV façade” of the Project 04. In this section, a specific example is provided in order to clarify the approach for the definition of fire safety requirements. Specifically, a conventional glass PV module is considered to be installed as glazing element of a double skin façade in a building located in Lugano, Switzerland.

4.2.2.1 Module/product level

As already introduced, when conventional glass PV module are installed as glazing elements of a double skin façade, they shall have both the IEC certification for PV products and the certification in accordance with the EN 14449.

With regard to the fire resistance requirements, the article about the fire resistance of the IEC 61730-2:2016 states that “**PV modules as building product** – i.e. serving as roof covering materials, **elements for building integration or that are mounted on buildings – are subject to specific safety requirements originating from national building codes**”. In particular, for glass PV modules (e.g. laminated glass) the fire resistance performance shall be tested in accordance with the EN 13501-2. In addition to the fire resistance test, the IEC 61730-2:2016 includes the **ignitability test** in order to evaluate if ignition occurs and the spread of flames due to an external fire source. Specifically, the test is based on the ISO 11925-2:2010 that – in the original version – is also **useful to assign the reaction to fire classification for building products** in accordance to the EN 13501-1:2009 (and amendments), which is also defined in the standard EN 14449 for the definition of the reaction to fire class for laminated glass and laminated safety glass.

As a consequence, performing the original version of the ISO 11925-2:2010 on a conventional glass PV module can allow to obtain the CE mark for PV modules as a construction product and also to identify the reaction to fire class of the product as a laminated glass in accordance to the EN 14449. This evaluation can allow to establish if the module under investigation (e.g. a conventional product serially produced and not intended for building use) is adequate to be

used in buildings, i.e. if the reaction to fire prescriptions stated in the national/local building codes are fulfilled.

4.2.2.2 Envelope system level

Once the reaction to fire class is defined as introduced in the previous paragraph 4.2.2.1, it is necessary to evaluate the requirements set in the national/local building standards about:

- Fire resistance
- Reaction to fire

depending on the final intended use of the PV module (glazing element) and the building envelope system (double skin façade).

As also discussed in the report “Fire safety of BIPV facades”, there are some specific fire resistance test methods for double skin façade, whose resulting performances shall be compared with the building requirements set at the local level, which include also the reaction to fire requirements. In the Swiss case, the relevant fire protection standards for buildings to consider are the following ones:

- VKF – Fire Protection Norm (1-15)
- VKF – Fire Protection Directives:
 - *Building materials and construction parts (13-15)*
 - *Use of building material (14-15)*
- VKF – Explanation Notes:
 - *Building with double skin facades (102-15)*
- VKF – Memorandum:
 - *Solar systems (2001-15)*

With regard to the reaction to fire requirement, the outer façade of the double skin system shall be realized with RF1 materials. However, three classes of fire safety requirements can be identified when specific double skin façade systems are conceived, as shown in Table 3.

Fire compartments of the building are extended also in the double skin facade	No fire compartments	Inner façade with fire resistance
No need for fire protection active system. If a fire protection active system is installed also in the cavity, material RF3 (cr) can be used for the outer skin.	Need for fire protection active system. If a fire protection active system is installed also in the cavity, material RF3 (cr) can be used for the outer skin.	No need for fire protection active system. If a fire protection active system is installed also in the cavity, material RF3 (cr) can be used for the outer skin.

Table 3 - three classes of fire safety requirements for double skin facades, in accordance with VKF regulations.

In conclusion, the use of conventional glass PV modules for BIPV projects shall be subjected to specific evaluations of the fire safety requirements that are typical of the building’s type and the building envelope’s system. It’s not possible to define a priori whether an element is applicable nor for some reference scenarios as i.e. described in the following case-studies.

For other details, see “Bonomo, P., Frontini, F., Saretta, E., Caccivio, M. Bellenda, G., Manzini, G. Cappellano, P.G. (2017) *Fire Safety of PV Modules and Buildings: Overviews, Bottlenecks and Hints, EU PVSEC 2017*”

From the previous paragraphs, it arises that it is not possible to give an “always-valid” answer to the question “is it possible to use conventional PV modules in BIPV projects?”. However, a methodology to deal with this issue can be proposed, as shown in figure 8, according to a performance-based approach. What is important to highlight is that the final intended building application and the regulative framework in force in the specific context about building requirements are two fundamental evaluations that are necessary to do in order to understand whether a conventional PV module can be used or not in BIPV projects.

Moreover, from the Figure 8, it arises that if a conventional PV module is not suitable or not compliant with reference building standards, it can be modified and, then, subjected to the applicable qualification procedures such as the IEC retesting procedure. Namely some building requirements can involve a re-design of the PV component (e.g. the glass or encapsulate typology or thickness) that, in turn, call to a further re-testing for the electro technical qualification. In detail, the retesting topic for a PV module is described in paragraph 6.

Figure 8. Proposed methodology to verify the suitability of conventional PV modules for BIPV projects. Indeed, the suitability depends on the fulfilment of building requirements, since a conventional PV module has already the IEC certification. However, changes in the PV module design to provide the required building performances involve the retesting in accordance to the IEC standards.

5 Case-studies: the use of conventional PV modules for BIPV skin

This chapter investigates the possibilities to use standard PV modules in a BIPV façade through some case-studies that show a real application of the above mentioned procedures and considerations. The qualification/certification process of products and reference normative will be discussed highlighting the applicability in the specific building and local context considered, from which also some border-line situations (under responsibility of planners/contractors/owners) and the risks arises from some missing gaps in the actual normative framework.

5.1 Case-study 1: BIPV façade for Palazzo Positivo in Chiasso-CH

The case-study is referred to an example of a ventilated PV facade installed on the north, south, east and west facades of a residential multi-family building in Chiasso, Ticino. The building is 25 meters high for 8 floors above ground. The external cladding is made of amorphous silicon PV modules with glass-glass structure.

Figure 9. Palazzo Positivo Chiasso

OBJECT	VALUE
Location	Chiasso
Typology of building	Residential
Year of construction	1965
Year of refurbishment	2013
Floors	8
Height	25 m
Typology	Ventilated facade

Table 4 – Case-study 1 data

The building skin system is opaque with a lightweight constructive system. The façade is micro ventilated and its U value is 0.12 W/m²K. The cladding is composed by toughened safety glass and photovoltaic glass panels. The chamber of ventilation is 27.1 mm wide and the substructure is certificate against falling hazard, fire resistance and deprived of thermal bridges (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Technical details of the façade of Palazzo Positivo

➤ Case 1: conventional PV modules for ventilated facade

In this paragraph is showed the list of the reference building normative for a glass ventilated façade with focus on safety in case of fire and mechanical safety (substructure and cladding). Norms considered in this analysis are both Swiss or European in order to have a complete overview. Furthermore, the normative framework is referred to the analysed real case-study and its specific parameters:

- Residential building located in Chiasso
- Building height 25 m (between 11 and 30 m a building is classified as medium height building - VKF)
- Ventilated facade
- External wall cladding made of glass

SAFETY IN CASE OF FIRE	MECHANICAL SAFETY	
I - FIRE	II - SUBSTRUCTURE	III - CLADDING - GLASS
<p>Figure: Ventilated PV facade by StoVerotec</p>		
<p>ETAG 034 Guideline for European technical approval of kits for external wall claddings – Part 1: Ventilated cladding kits comprising cladding components and associated fixings EN 13501-1:2009 Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 1: Classification using data from reaction to fire tests Fire control guideline 14-15:2017 Application of building material SIA 260:2013 Basis of structural design SIA 261:2014 Actions on structures UPI Glass in architecture UNI 7697:2015 Safety criteria for glazing applications EN 14449:2005 Glass in building. Laminated glass and laminated safety glass. Evaluation of conformity/product standard. SN EN 12600 Glass in building - Pendulum test - Impact test method and classification for flat glass</p>		

The previous table collected all the main prescription arising for this building façade with the normative references indicating the essential minimal requirements so that a PV standard module could be classified as a BIPV module for ventilated facade. Data are referred to the substructure, the cladding, the fire safety of the case-study. Below a flowchart is reported showing the workflow needed to assess if a standard module can be used in the building skin by evaluating some specific requirements.

➤ **Case 2: conventional PV modules for curtain wall**

Below is showed the list of the reference building normative for curtain wall with a focus on safety in case of fire and mechanical safety.

SAFETY IN CASE OF FIRE		MECHANICAL SAFETY													
<p>I - FIRE</p>															
<p>EN 13830:2015 The reaction to fire of components used in curtain walling kit should be evaluated when relevant. The test method to evaluate the reaction to fire performance are defined in the standard EN 13501-1:2009. The fire resistance shall be tested in accordance with EN 1364-3:2014 and EN 1364-4:2014 that are classified in accordance with EN 13501-2:2009.</p>	<p>EN 13830 This European Standard specifies requirements of curtain walling kit intended to be used as a building envelope to provide also safety in use and provides test/assessments/calculation methods and compliance criteria of the related performances:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resistance to wind loads with EN 12179 and EN 13116 Impact resistance with EN 14019 / SIA 329:2012 or SN EN 12600 	<p>SIA 329:2012 It specifies the maximum admissible bending tension in N/mm² for each glass typology used on curtain walls.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Glass</th> <th>N/mm²</th> <th>Norm</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>ESG¹</td> <td>50-30</td> <td>SN EN 12150-1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>VSG²</td> <td>50-22</td> <td>SN EN ISO 12543-1-2 EN 14449:2005</td> </tr> <tr> <td>TVG³</td> <td>29-18</td> <td>SN EN 1863-1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>¹ Toughened safety glass ² Laminated safety glass ³ Heat strengthened soda lime silicate glass</p>	Glass	N/mm ²	Norm	ESG ¹	50-30	SN EN 12150-1	VSG ²	50-22	SN EN ISO 12543-1-2 EN 14449:2005	TVG ³	29-18	SN EN 1863-1	
Glass	N/mm ²	Norm													
ESG ¹	50-30	SN EN 12150-1													
VSG ²	50-22	SN EN ISO 12543-1-2 EN 14449:2005													
TVG ³	29-18	SN EN 1863-1													
	<p>SIA 260:2013 and 261:2014 As building construction products, glazing panels have to be designed to comply with the wind, snow and mechanical loads.</p>	<p>UPI In case of falling hazard is necessary to employ a laminated safety glass.</p> <p>UNI 7697:2015 / Italy It shows different practical cases specifying which is the correct glass to use. In order to avoid the falling hazard, considering curtain walling facades, is necessary to use a laminated safety glass.</p> <p>Figure: Zaulek Piękna, Warsaw, Poland</p>													
<p>EN 13830:2015 Curtain walling - Product standard EN 13501-1:2009 Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 1: Classification using data from reaction to fire tests EN 1364-3:2014 Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 3: Curtain walling - Full configuration (complete assembly) EN 1364-4:2014 Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 3: Curtain walling - Part configuration EN 13501-2:2009 Fire classification of construction products and building elements – Part 2: Classification using data from fire resistance tests, excluding ventilation services EN 13830 Curtain walling EN 12179 Curtain walling - Resistance to wind load - Test method EN 13116 Curtain walling - Resistance load - Performance requirements EN 14019 / SIA 329:2012 Curtain walling - Product standard SN EN 12600 Glass in building - Pendulum test - Impact test method and classification for flat glass SIA 260:2013 Basis of structural design SIA 261:2014 Actions on structures SN EN 12150 Glass in building - Thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description SN EN ISO 12543-1/-2 Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 1: Definitions and description of component parts - Part 2: Laminated safety glass EN 14449:2005 Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Evaluation of conformity/Product standard SN EN 1863-1 Glass in building - Heat strengthened soda lime silicate glass - Part 1: Definition and description UPI Glass in architecture- SIGAB Directive 002 Safety with glass - requirements for glass components UNI 7697:2015 Safety criteria for glazing applications</p>															

In the graphic below are showed the normative references that indicate the essential minimal requirements so that a PV standard module could be classified as a BIPV module for curtain wall. Data are referred to the structure, the cladding, the fire safety of the case-study and related corrective actions.

➤ **Case 3: conventional PV modules for double skin facade**

Below is showed the list of the reference building normative for double skin facade with focus on safety in case of fire, structure and cladding made of glass. Regarding the cladding and the structure double skin facades are assimilated to the curtain wall.

SAFETY IN CASE OF FIRE		MECHANICAL SAFETY										
<p>I - FIRE</p>												
<p>Fire control explicatory note 102-15 The external wall envelope and the thermal insulation of the internal façade and the external façade must be built with RF1 construction materials; curtains or venetian blinds, for medium height buildings (11-30 m), with RF2. The compartment must have a fire resistance EI30 and must be hermetically connected with the external façade or continuous until the external side of the external façade.</p> <p>For different typologies of double skin facades referring to the fire control explicatory note 102-15.</p>	<p>EN 13830 This European Standard specifies requirements of curtain walling kit intended to be used as a building envelope to provide also safety in use and provides test/assessments/calculation methods and compliance criteria of the related performances.</p> <p>There are different typologies of double skin façades and each of them have different characteristic.</p>	<p>SIA 329:2012 It specifies the maximum admissible bending tension in N/mm² for each glass typology used on curtain walls. It is assumed similar for double skin facades.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="992 913 1366 1008"> <tr> <td>ESG¹</td> <td>50-30</td> <td>SN EN 12150-1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>VSG²</td> <td>50-22</td> <td>SN EN ISO 12543-1-2 EN 14449:2005</td> </tr> <tr> <td>TVG³</td> <td>29-18</td> <td>SN EN 1863-1</td> </tr> </table> <p>¹ Toughened safety glass ² Laminated safety glass ³ Heat strengthened soda lime silicate glass</p>		ESG ¹	50-30	SN EN 12150-1	VSG ²	50-22	SN EN ISO 12543-1-2 EN 14449:2005	TVG ³	29-18	SN EN 1863-1
ESG ¹	50-30	SN EN 12150-1										
VSG ²	50-22	SN EN ISO 12543-1-2 EN 14449:2005										
TVG ³	29-18	SN EN 1863-1										
<p>SIA 329:2012 SIA 329 underlines the evaluation methods for physical properties of facades. It evaluates the shocks resistance, internal (SN EN 14019) and external (SN EN 12600).</p>		<p>UPI In case of falling hazard is necessary to employ a laminated safety glass.</p> <p>UNI 7697:2015 It shows different practical cases specifying which is the correct glass to use. In order to avoid the falling hazard, considering curtain walling facades, is necessary to use a laminated safety glass.</p> <p>Figure: Italwindows</p>										
<p>102-15 Building with double skin facades SIA 260:2013 Basis of structural design SIA 261:2014 Actions on structures SIA 329:2012 Curtain walling - Product standard SN EN 12150 Glass in building - Thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description SN EN ISO 12543-1/-2 Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 1: Definitions and description of component parts - Part 2: Laminated safety glass EN 14449:2005 Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Evaluation of conformity/Product standard SN EN 1863-1 Glass in building - Heat strengthened soda lime silicate glass - Part 1: Definition and description SN EN 14019 Curtain walling, impact resistance, performance requirements UPI Glass in architecture- SIGAB Directive 002 Safety with glass - requirements for glass components SN EN 12600 Glass in building - Pendulum test - Impact test method and classification for flat glass UNI 7697:2015 Safety criteria for glazing applications EN 13830 Curtain walling</p>												

In the graphic below are shown the normative references that indicate the essential minimal requirements so that a PV standard module could be classified as a BIPV module for double skin facade. Data are referred to the structure, the cladding, the fire safety of the case-study and related corrective actions.

➤ **Final considerations of the case-study**

From previous analysis emerges that the European normative and guidelines include detailed information and norms related to the design procedure of ventilated facades (ETAG 034), curtain walls and double skin facades (EN 13839). There are not further additions from the Swiss normative framework considered that define in greater detail prescriptions or rules for evaluating the mechanical safety of facades. The Swiss fire safety prescriptions, as a national code, define all the reference rules for fire safety.

The analysis for ventilated façade, curtain wall and double skin facade in the specific case-studies showed that a standard PV module can be considered a BIPV module only when:

- Considering the mechanical safety of the substructure: actions on structures are verified according to SIA 261
- Considering the mechanical safety of cladding made of glass: the glass chosen satisfy specific parameters related to conditions where the system is installed (glass falling hazard)
- Considering the fire safety: the ventilated façade must be projected according to the Swiss guideline or explicatory notes and must be approved by VKF
- To summarize: all requirements of mechanical and fire safety are satisfied together

If requirements are not satisfied is necessary to adopt corrective actions (e.g. adoption of another component or modification/customization of the component under consideration) and re-evaluate that the applicable requirements are satisfied.

5.2 Case-study 2: BIPV balconies for a multifamily social housing building

This case-study 2 is referred to a PV system with a glass-glass system installed as railing on the balconies of a residential building located in Chiasso. The building is 26 meters high (Figure 11). Data of the system are showed on Table 5.

Figure 11. Railing of Palazzo Positivo

OBJECT	VALUE
Location	Chiasso
Typology of building	Residential
Year of construction	1969
Year of refurbishment	-
Floors	8
Height of building	26 m
Typology	Balcony

Table 5 – Case study 2 data

➤ **Case 1: conventional PV modules for railings**

Below is showed the reference building normative for railings with focus on dimensional parameters, structure and glass. The Swiss normative framework related to the railing design is exhaustive. It was not necessary to introduce the European regulation.

The normative framework is referred to the analysed case study:

- Residential building located in Chiasso
- Railing

- Railing protection made of glass

FALLING HAZARD	MECHANICAL SAFETY											
<p data-bbox="159 347 510 376">I – DIMENSIONAL PARAMETERS</p> <p data-bbox="989 638 1364 728">UPI A laminated safety glass is recommended for glass railings.</p> <p data-bbox="989 750 1364 952">SN EN 12600 This European Standard specifies a pendulum impact test method for single flat panes of glass for use in buildings. The test is intended to classify flat glass products in three principal classes by performance under impact and by mode of breakage.</p> <p data-bbox="989 974 1364 1131">UNI 7697:2015 / Italy It shows different practical cases specifying which is the correct glass to use. In order to avoid the falling hazard, considering curtain walling facades, is necessary to use a laminated safety glass.</p>												
Glass	VSG											
Minimum railing height	100 cm											
High buildings min. parapet height	110 cm											
Height fall	> 12 m											
Q _k value of horizontal loads (residential-cat. A)	0.8 kN/m											
<p data-bbox="143 1332 327 1355">Value suggested by UPI</p> <p data-bbox="143 1377 917 1579">SIA 358:2010 Railings SIA 261:2014 Actions on structures SIA 262:2013 Concrete structures SIA 263:2013 Steel structures - Supplementary specifications SIA 265:2012 Timber structures SIA 179:1998 Fixings inside concrete and walls UPI Glass in architecture- SIGAB Directive 002. Safety with glass - requirements for glass components SN EN 12600 Glass in building - Pendulum test - Impact test method and classification for flat glass UNI 7697:2015 Safety criteria for glazing applications</p>	<p data-bbox="566 1310 813 1332">Figure: Palazzo Positivo Chiasso</p>	<p data-bbox="989 1310 1212 1332">Figure: Private house in Lasa</p>										

In the graphic below is shown the normative framework for railings in order to verify when a standard PV module can be used as BIPV. In the following analysis is considered the structure, the glass and related corrective actions.

➤ **Final considerations of the case-study**

Compared to analysed facades, in which in Switzerland is missing a precise normative regulation, the reference normative framework for railings is more detailed and includes clear requirements to follow. The norm SIA 261 and SIA 358 are the Swiss reference for the railing design.

A standard PV module can be considered as BIPV module for railings when:

- Considering the mechanical safety of the structure, actions on structures are satisfied according with the SIA 261 (section “railings”)
- Considering the mechanical safety of the glass, it is necessary to consider the falling hazard and the place of glass installation

If results are not positive is necessary to adopt corrective actions (e.g. adoption of another component or modification/customization of the component under consideration) and re-evaluate that the applicable requirements are satisfied.

6 Testing procedures to qualify a PV module for BIPV applications

As already introduced in paragraph 4.3 and from the case study analysis in paragraph 5, the use of conventional PV modules in BIPV projects must be subjected to specific evaluation of the final intended use in building and to the assessment of the relative building requirements.

Indeed, even though conventional PV modules have already the IEC certification, this does not mean that they can be used in BIPV projects as building element without any further evaluation or assessment. This is due to the fact that a BIPV application, as a part of the building envelope, has to guarantee specific performances, which are defined in the building standards and, therefore, also conventional PV modules shall contribute to guarantee the building performances requested.

As a result, depending on the BIPV project – namely, the building envelope application- the legislative framework has to be defined in order to verify the suitability of conventional PV modules for such an application. Indeed, the suitability and applicability depends on the fulfilment of building performances. In many cases the “building assessment” leads to corrective actions in the module’s design in order to make the component compliant to the building skin use. However, if the corrective action implies **changes in the PV module design, this not only will involve the assessment according to the applicable building standards but it also will imply the retesting in accordance to the IEC standards.**

In detail, the procedure for the retesting of a PV module are defined in the IEC Retesting Guideline *“Product or Process Modifications Requiring Limited CBTL Retesting to Maintain Safety Certification for IEC 61730-1:2004 Ed. 1.0 and IEC 61730-2:2004 Ed. 1.0”*. As stated in this guideline, “Changes in material selection, components and manufacturing process can impact the safety of the modified product” so, some additional tests are required to maintain the safety requirements depending on the following modifications:

- a) Change in cell technology,
- b) Modification to encapsulation system,
- c) Modification to superstrate,
- d) Modification to back-sheet/substrate,
- e) Modification to frame and/or mounting structure,
- f) Modification to junction box/electrical termination,
- g) Change in cell interconnect materials or technique,
- h) Change in electrical circuit of an identical package,
- i) Higher power output (by 10% or more) in the identical package including size and using the identical cell process,
- j) Qualification of a frameless module after the design has received certification as a framed module.

While, the following modifications don’t require re-testing:

- fewer cells in module,
- smaller cells in module, as long as each cell has the same number of interconnects and equivalent numbers of solder bonds per unit area,
- up to 20% larger module area with the same number of cells.

It is important to highlight that, a draft of a IEC Technical Specification – the IEC DTS 62915 “Photovoltaic (PV) modules - Retesting for type approval, design and safety qualification”, is under development and will provide some changes in the process.

In example, if a conventional PV module is used as opaque cladding of a ventilated façade, among several requirements, it shall guarantee an adequate mechanical resistance to withstand the wind load without damages or permanent deformations. If the conventional PV module is not able to fulfil this requirements, its structure shall be modified. As an example, among possible solutions, the front glass thickness shall be increased (or the glass type changed) or the rear mounting structure should be modified. In both cases, thus, there is the need to retest the conventional PV module as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Example of a procedure to verify the suitability of the conventional PV module to be used in a BIPV project, with a specific focus on the IEC retesting for two modifications in the PV module design.

However, not only changes to fulfil building requirements can be done, but in BIPV sector often changes in the aesthetics, especially on the front glass of a conventional PV module, are requested in order to obtain a more appealing pattern or design. In this case, the “architectural” customization involves similarly the retesting of the PV module. In the following chapter a case-study, developed with the frame of Active Interfaces project, is reported.

This means that, nowadays, the use of a PV element (e.g. a PV module) in building skin has to be evaluated case by case in the single project according to the approach above explained. If the performance-based evaluation is positive the component can be used as a construction component otherwise corrective

actions have to be undertaken. If structural modifications are applied to the component this often bring to the need to double-check the qualification issues for electro technical and building normative.

6.1 Case study: IEC type approval and certification of a multi-coloured BIPV module - Definition of the relevant modifications introduced by the colouring technique and different module size according to the IEC re-testing guidelines.

A specific example of a full qualification program and type approval (according to IEC 61215:2016 and IEC 61730:2016) for a family of colored BIPV modules, designed by HSLU and Userhuus, has been developed by SUPSI PVLab: based on the technical specification IEC TS 62915 – “Photovoltaic (PV) modules – Type approval, design and safety qualification – Retesting”, one type of multi-coloured BIPV module has been submitted to a full testing program (parent product for type approval), according to the combined design qualification (IEC 61215) and safety (IEC 61730) test flow (see figure below).

Figure 10 Testing test flow program (parent product for type approval), according to the combined design (IEC 61215) and safety (IEC 61730) qualification. (to be simplified)

Figure 11. Original PV module. Type 1: RE100. Relative Efficiency 100 72 mono-cells Active wire 1972 x 1000 cm frameless Glass-glass 2x4mm Covers: Any size until 2400 x 1200 mm (identical construction and material, fewer cells) (source: Userhuus)

Figure 12. Re-tested module. Type4: Relative Efficiency 75, 72 mono-cells, Active wire 1972 x 1000 cm frameless Glass-glass 2x4mm. This module, due to the new layering, namely the colouring of the front glass, has been subjected to a full qualification program and type approval. (source: Userhuus).

6.1.1 Power output

Subsequently, a number of variants derived from the type-tested model, have been selected by the manufacturer and submitted to a reduced re-testing sequences, in order to maintain the initial qualification and extend the validity to a wide range of products derived from the approved parent product. This approach guarantee the quality of the whole family of products and to save time and cost of certification.

In particular, all the variants with higher or lower output power (by 10 % or more, due to the variation of the transmittance of the coloring layer), with identical design and size and using the identical cell process, have been submitted to re-testing, according to IEC TS 6195, cl. 4.2.12:

For IEC 61215, the following tests have been repeated on samples showing higher or lower output power (due to a different coloring):

- *Hot-spot endurance test*
- *Thermal cycling test, 200 cycles*
- *Bypass diode thermal test*

For IEC 61730, the following safety test has been repeated:

- *Reverse current overload test*

6.1.2 Size variations

In order to further extend the validity of the certification of the BIPV family of products as described above, other aspects, from a constructive point of view, have been considered: in particular, the dimensional customization of the BIPV products, that are related mainly with the structural and mechanical characterization. According to IEC 61915, the following re-testing procedure has been followed to cover the size variations:

cl. 4.2.11 Change in PV module size

For increase by more than 20 % of length, width or area

Repeat for IEC 61215:

- • *Thermal cycling test, 200 cycles*
- • *Damp heat test*
- • *Static mechanical load test*
- • *Hail test (if non-tempered glass or if non-glass)*

Repeat for IEC 61730:

- • *Module breakage test (MST 32)*

As a result of the above qualification program, a whole family of multi-colored BIPV modules with identical design and using the identical cell process, but with different colors, power outputs and sizes gained an IEC certificate according to IEC 61215:2016 series and IEC 61730:2016.

7 Conclusions

The core topic of this report can be simplified with a basic question: “can a conventional PV module be used in BIPV project as a construction component?”.

This issue has been investigated throughout the analysis of the BIPV requirements, in accordance with both the IEC and the relevant building standards in accordance with the EN 50583:2016. Since the goal of this report was to understand the potential to apply “conventional/standard” PV modules for BIPV projects with regard to its normative compliance, after clarifying what a “conventional/standard”, we discussed some of the key-topics related to the performance levels and qualification issues regarding the application in building skin. In detail, the glass safety, mechanical and fire properties for facade application have been used through a more in-depth analysis on some real case-studies, to better explain and clarify the need of a performance-based approach and the workflows needed to assess the normative compliance of a BIPV component.

It’s emerged that, since in principle a conventional PV module has not been developed for building integration, the specific building requirements for the final intended use in the building skin shall be identified and the related performances of the component must be verified, to assess if the element can be used in building envelope. Formally, if the EN 50583:2016 is applied, this is also necessary to obtain the correct qualification for applying a CE-mark as a construction product according to CPR 305/2011.

As it arises also from the case studies, such a methodology shall be applied for each BIPV project, because the required performances can vary depending on the BIPV project location, the building’s geometry and typology, the use as well as the envelope system and the specific conventional PV module. In particular, when a conventional PV module is not capable to provide the performances required by the building codes in force, it must be modified to achieve a satisfactory level of performances (and consequently often also subjected to a retesting procedure in accordance with the IEC guidelines).

Therefore, it is not possible to give an “always-valid” answer to the main question above mentioned. Nevertheless, a methodology to deal with this issue has been proposed, grounding on two fundamental aspects: the final intended building application and the performance-based assessment according to the regulative framework about PV and building requirements. Moreover, as explained in the last chapter, an optimization of the test sequences for the IEC type approval can be also achieved for a family of customized modules thus representing an advantage for the producer.

Once clarified the final intended use in the building skin of the PV element, in many cases the standards in force (e.g. building codes) can be applied to BIPV elements (conventional or not) to verify an adequate performance level for the building use (e.g. this is already adopted in many BIPV glasses for a performance assessment like the safety glass, mechanical resistance, g-value, U-value, etc.).

However some missing gaps are still calling for further research since BIPV requirements cannot be considered the simple sum of building and PV ones, so that the developments of new testing procedure for a performance-based approach is still a relevant question for BIPV.